

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF LOCALLY MADE LEARNING RESOURCES ON LEARNERS' ATTENTIVENESS AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT

This study described the level of effectiveness of locally-made learning resources, the level of learners' attentiveness, and learners' academic performance. This study aims to provide public schools and learning centers (teachers and learners) with diverse, quality, accessible, cost-effective, and appropriate learning resources to have effective and efficient learning outcomes. Descriptive and correlational methods with a questionnaire as a primary tool of data collection were used to find the effect of locally made learning resources on the attentiveness and academic performance of the learners. The descriptive method was utilized to measure the level of effectiveness of the locally made learning resources, the level of attentiveness, and the level of academic performance of the learners. The correlational method was used to determine whether or not there is a relationship between the level of effectiveness of locally made learning resources and level of attentiveness of the learners and academic performance of learners. The sample was taken from 3 junior high schools. A total of 279 learners were randomly selected from these school in proportion to its population. Spearman rank-order correlation was used to determine the relationship between the level of effectiveness of locally made learning resources and the level of learners' attentiveness. It was also used to determine the relationship between the level of effectiveness of locally made learning resources and the level of learners' academic performance. Computed rho values indicated that the effectiveness of locally-made learning resources highly and positively influences the level of attentiveness of learners and their academic performance.

Keywords: *Locally-Made Learning Resources; Learners' Attentiveness; Academic Performance*

INTRODUCTION

Education plays a crucial role in shaping individuals' lives and societies as a whole. In recent years, there has been a growing interest in exploring innovative teaching methods and learning resources to enhance students' attentiveness and academic performance. One such approach is the utilization of locally-made learning resources, which are designed and developed within the local context to cater to the specific needs of learners. This study aims to investigate the effectiveness of locally-made learning resources on learners' attentiveness and academic performance.

Learning Resources play a vital role in transferring information or ideas from the teacher to the learner. The learning resources aid the delivery of class instructions; may it be physical or virtual. Locally made or contextualized learning resources are made to address the specific needs of a group of learners. Learning Resources can be text and non-text-based as defined by the Bureau of Learning Resources under the Department of Education. Text-based learning resources consist of books, magazines, and other printed materials. On the other hand, non-text-based learning resources are equipment and apparatus.

Learning resources play a significant part in the delivery of instructions. It may serve as the primary source of lessons that are part of the curriculum. It can aid the teacher in the clarification of introduced ideas. It may also significantly affect the learner's interest or attentiveness. Different learning resources may have different impacts on learners. A learner may be attracted to specific learning resources but not to other learning resources. Thus, it is essential to choose the right learning resources to be used. The correct use of learning resources may effectively catch the attention of learners.

Attentiveness is a crucial aspect of effective learning, as it directly influences students' ability to absorb and retain information. By incorporating locally-made learning resources, educators can create a learning environment that captures students' attention and fosters active participation. These resources can include visual aids, interactive materials, and multimedia content that align with the local culture, language, and educational context (Kumar & Kumar, 2017).

Furthermore, academic performance is a key indicator of students' learning outcomes and success. By tailoring learning resources to the local context, educators can potentially enhance students' understanding, motivation, and overall academic achievement. Locally-made resources have the potential to bridge the gap between abstract concepts and real-life applications, making learning more meaningful and impactful (Barron et al., 2015).

Research has shown that the use of learning resources can significantly impact students' engagement and learning outcomes (Barron et al., 2015; Hattie, 2009). However, the majority of existing studies have focused on commercially-produced learning resources, often overlooking the potential benefits of locally-made resources.

This research gap highlights the need to explore the effectiveness of locally-made learning resources and their impact on learners' attentiveness and academic performance. Locally-made learning resources have the advantage of being culturally relevant, context-specific, and cost-effective, making them potentially more accessible and relatable to learners (Kumar & Kumar, 2017).

By examining the impact of locally-made learning resources on learners' attentiveness and academic performance, this study aims to contribute to the existing body of knowledge on effective teaching practices. The findings will provide valuable insights for educators, curriculum developers, and policymakers, highlighting the potential benefits of incorporating locally-made resources into educational settings.

Research Questions

The main purpose of this study was to determine the effectiveness of locally-made learning resources on the learners' attentiveness and their academic performance.

This study answers the following questions:

1. What is the level of effectiveness of locally made learning resources?
2. What is the level of attentiveness of learners?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the level of effectiveness of locally made learning resources and the level of attentiveness of learners?
4. What is the level of academic performance of the learners?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the level of effectiveness of locally made learning resources and the learners' academic performance?

METHODOLOGY

The researcher used the descriptive-correlational method to find the effect of locally made learning resources on the attentiveness and academic performance of the learners. The descriptive method was utilized to measure the level of effectiveness of the locally made learning resources, the level of attentiveness, and the level of academic performance of the learners. The correlational method was used to determine whether or not there is a relationship between the level of effectiveness of locally made learning resources and level of attentiveness of the learners and academic performance of learners. The sample was taken from 3 junior high schools under the city schools division of Dipolog City. A total of 279 learners were randomly selected from these school in proportion to its population. Spearman rank-order correlation was used to determine the relationship between the level of effectiveness of locally made learning resources and the level of learners' attentiveness. It was also used to determine the relationship between the level of effectiveness of locally made learning resources and the level of learners' academic performance.

The researcher used questionnaires to gather data from the respondents. The questionnaires aimed to collect relevant data, which led to the conclusion on the effectiveness of locally made learning resources to the learners' attentiveness and

academic performance. It was carefully crafted by the researcher and was anchored on the Alternative Delivery Mode Learning Resource Standards of the Department of Education, with ten (10) items to assess the effectiveness of the locally made learning resources and another ten (10) items to determine learners' level of attentiveness was given to the respondents through an online form. The respondents were asked to read the statements reflected in the questionnaire. They were asked to choose the degree of relevance and their agreement on the statements regarding the effectiveness of locally made learning resources and learners' attentiveness towards locally made learning resources, respectively. The degree of relevance is based on the scale and equivalents as 4 = Highly Relevant; 3= Relevant; 2= Somewhat Relevant; and 1= Not Relevant, while the degree of agreement on the attentiveness of learners to the locally made learning resources is scaled as 4= Strongly Agree; 3= Agree; 2= Disagree; 1= Strongly Disagree. The questions asked were based on the items in the Learning Object Review Instrument as part of the study, A Framework for Evaluating the Quality Multimedia Learning Resources authored by Leacock and Nesbit (2007) and the Alternative Delivery Mode Learning Resource Standards of the Department of Education (2019), which the researcher considered to be suitable with this study. The research instrument that was used to gather data in this study had been subjected to validity and reliability tests with coefficients 0.76 and 0.74, respectively.

Weighted mean and standard deviation were used to describe the level of effectiveness of locally made learning resources as perceived by the learners, their level of attentiveness, and mean percentage score.

The following statistical continuum was used to interpret the level of effectiveness of locally made learning resources:

SCALE	STATISTICAL CONTINUUM	DESCRIPTION	INTERPRETATION
4	3.25 – 4.00	Highly Relevant	Very Effective
3	2.50 – 3.24	Relevant	Effective
2	1.75 – 2.49	Somewhat Relevant	Slightly Effective
1	1.00 – 1.74	Not Relevant	Not Effective

The following statistical continuum was used to interpret the level of learners' attentiveness:

SCALE	STATISTICAL CONTINUUM	DESCRIPTION	INTERPRETATION
4	3.25 – 4.00	Strongly Agree	Very Attentive
3	2.50 – 3.24	Agree	Attentive
2	1.75 – 2.49	Disagree	Slightly Attentive
1	1.00 – 1.74	Strongly Disagree	Not Attentive

The following statistical continuum was used to interpret the level of learners' academic performance:

SCALE	RANGE	PERFORMANCE LEVEL	DESCRIPTIVE EQUIVALENT
5	4.51 – 5.00	96 – 100	Mastered
4	3.51 – 4.50	86 – 95	Closely Approximating Mastery

3	2.51 – 3.50	66 – 85	Moving Towards Mastery
2	1.51 – 2.50	35 – 65	Average Mastery
1	1.00 – 1.50	0 – 34	Low Mastery

Spearman rank-order correlation was used to determine the relationship between the level of effectiveness of locally made learning resources and the level of learners' attentiveness. It was also used to determine the relationship between the level of effectiveness of locally made learning resources and the level of learners' academic performance. The data were analyzed using MS Excel and Jamovi v. 2.3.19. The relationship was tested using a .05 level of significance.

RESULTS

The Level of Effectiveness of Locally-Made Learning Resources is shown in Table 1.

Table 1

The Level of Effectiveness of Locally Made Learning Resources

Statements	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
1. The content of the Support Material for Independent Learning Engagement (SMILE) Module to the actual topic discussed	3.16	.60	Effective
2. The review lesson presented in the SMILE Module to the present topic discussed	3.18	.61	Effective
3. The examples presented in the SMILE Module to the topic discussed	3.19	.65	Effective
4. The graph and tables presented in the SMILE Module to the topic discussed	3.09	.65	Effective
5. The pictures presented in the SMILE Module to the topic discussed	3.04	.68	Effective
6. The assessment in the SMILE Module to the lesson discussed	3.23	.66	Effective
7. The difficulty of the assessment in the SMILE Module to learner's grade level	3.12	.66	Effective
8. The font size and style used in the SMILE Module to the learner's grade level	3.21	.67	Effective
9. The total length or volume of the SMILE Module to the learner's grade level	3.09	.64	Effective

10. The words and sentences used in the discussion of the SMILE Module to the learner's grade level	3.22	.64	Effective
Grand Weighted Mean	3.15	.65	Effective
1.00 – 1.75 Not Relevant/Not Effective	1.76 – 2.50 Somewhat Relevant/	Slightly Effective	
2.51 – 3.25 Relevant/Effective	3.26 – 4.00 Highly Relevant/Very	Effective	

The Level of Attentiveness of the Learners is shown in Table 2.

Table 2

The Level of Attentiveness of the Learners

Statement	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
1. The content of the Support Material for Independent Learning Engagement (SMILE) Module catches your attention.	3.22	.50	Attentive
2. The review lessons presented encourage you to read the new topic.	3.24	.58	Attentive
3. The graph and tables in the SMILE Module catch your interest.	3.11	.56	Attentive
4. The presentation of ideas of the SMILE Module encourages you to read even more.	3.18	.59	Attentive
5. The sequence of thought of the SMILE Module draws your attention.	3.11	.57	Attentive
6. The assessment draws your desire to think.	3.19	.58	Attentive
7. The pictures in the SMILE Module catch your interest.	3.11	.57	Attentive
8. The idea that you are using a locally-made learning resource encourages you to read.	3.21	.50	Attentive
9. The font style and size attract you to read.	3.14	.56	Attentive
10. The total length or volume of the SMILE Module encourages you to finish reading the module.	3.17	.56	Attentive
Grand Weighted Mean	3.17	.56	Attentive
1.00 – 1.75 Strongly Disagree/Not Attentive	1.76 – 2.50 Disagree/Slightly	Attentive	
2.51 – 3.25 Agree/Attentive	3.26 – 4.00 Strongly Agree/Very	Attentive	

The Relationship Between the Level of Effectiveness of Locally-Made Learning Resources and Level of Attentiveness of the Learners is shown in Table 3.

Table 3

The Relationship Between the Level of Effectiveness of Locally-Made Learning Resources and Level of Attentiveness of the Learners

Variables	Computed rho (ρ)	P-Value	Interpretation
Effectiveness of Locally Made Learning Resources and Attentiveness of Learners	0.662	0.000	Large/High Positive Correlation/ Significant

The Level of Academic Performance of the Learners is shown in Table 4.

Table 4

The Level of Academic Performance of the Learners

MPS	FREQUENCY	Descriptive Equivalent
96 – 100	0	Mastered
86 – 95	0	Closely Approximating Mastery
66 – 85	80	Moving Toward Mastery
35 – 65	199	Average Mastery
0 – 34	0	Low Mastery
TOTAL	279	-
Average Weighted Value	2.29	Average Mastery
Standard Deviation	.98	-
1.00 – 1.50 Low Mastery	1.51 – 2.50 Average Mastery	
2.51 – 3.50 Moving Towards Mastery	3.51 – 4.50 Closely Approximating Mastery	
4.51 – 5.00 Mastered		

The Relationship Between the Level of Effectiveness of Locally-Made Learning Resources and the Learners' Academic Performance is shown in Table 5.

Table 5

The Relationship Between the Level of Effectiveness of Locally-Made Learning Resources and the Learners' Academic Performance

Variables	Computed rho (ρ)	P-Value	Interpretation
Effectiveness of Locally Made Learning Resources and Learner's Academic Performance	0.182	0.002	Small/Low Positive Correlation/ Significant

DISCUSSION

Table 1 presents the level of effectiveness of locally made learning resources. The table shows the statements, weighted mean, standard deviation, grand weighted mean, level of relevance, and implication. The weighted means in each of the statements were all in the range of 2.51 – 3.25. This means that the learners perceived that the locally-made learning resources was relevant and effective. The grand weighted mean, 3.15, with a standard deviation of 0.65, indicates that the learners found that the locally-made learning resources is an effective learning resource. Locally made learning resources are effective because they were often designed to align with the cultural context and needs of the local community. Locally made learning resources are effective because they were often designed to align with the cultural context and needs of the local community. This cultural relevance can enhance students' engagement and motivation, as they can relate to the content more easily. It is created in the local language can improve students' understanding and comprehension and should incorporate real-life examples, local case studies, and relevant scenarios that resonate with students' experiences. The result is consistent with Oni's (1992) statement that instructional resources are teachers' strategic factors in organizing and providing education. Additionally, Okongo et al. (2015) opined that in order to raise the quality of education, its efficiency and productivity, better teaching-learning materials (TLM), physical facilities, and human resources are needed.

Table 2 presents the level of attentiveness of the learners. The table shows the statement, weighted mean, standard deviation, grand weighted mean, level of agreement, and implication. The computed values of the weighted means in each statement were all in the range 2.51 – 3.25. This means that the locally-made learning resources catch the interest and attention of the learners. The grand weighted mean, 3.17, with a standard deviation of 0.56, indicates that the learners agree that the locally made learning resources captured their attention and it encourages them to read the material. It is important to note that the effectiveness of locally-made learning resources in promoting attentiveness also depends on the quality of their design, instructional strategies used by

teachers, and the overall learning environment. Therefore, it is crucial for educators to receive appropriate training and support in utilizing these resources effectively to maximize their impact on learners' attentiveness. Making use of engaging educational resources to capture students' attention during lessons enhances the significance of time spent in school. This is consistent with the statement of Shaw (2018.) that it's the material students engage with to better themselves, meet their goals, and ultimately succeed in your course.

Table 3 presents the relationship between the level of effectiveness of locally made learning resources and the level of attentiveness of the learners. The table shows the variables, computed rho ρ , P-value, and interpretation. The computed rho ρ value, 0.662, produced a P-value that is less than 0.05 level of significance. This means that there was a significant relationship between the level of effectiveness of locally made learning resources and the level of attentiveness of the learners. It implies that the level of effectiveness of locally-made learning resources highly and positively influences the level of attentiveness of learners. Locally-made learning resources can be tailored to address specific local challenges, needs, and interests. By addressing topics and issues that are relevant to learners' lives and communities, these resources can spark curiosity and engagement, leading to increased attentiveness. Well-designed locally-made learning resources can incorporate visually appealing elements, such as colorful illustrations, diagrams, and multimedia components. These visual elements can capture learners' attention and make the content more engaging. Additionally, interactive features, such as hands-on activities or interactive digital tools, can further enhance attentiveness by encouraging active participation and exploration. When teachers use locally-made resources effectively, they can connect with learners on a personal level, fostering a sense of trust and rapport. This positive relationship can contribute to increased attentiveness as learners feel valued and supported in their learning journey. The result supported the study of Nyongesa et al. (2015) as it revealed that teaching and learning resources help improve access and educational outcomes since students are less likely to be absent from schools that provide interesting, meaningful, and relevant experiences to them. These resources should be provided in quality and quantity in schools for an effective teaching-learning process.

Table 4 presents the level of academic performance of the learners. The table shows the MPS, frequency, descriptive equivalent, average weighted value, and standard deviation. Eighty learners (80) have MPS between 66 – 85 with a mastery level of “*Moving Toward Mastery*” and one-hundred ninety-nine (199) learners have MPS between 55 – 65 with a mastery level of “*Average Mastery*”. The level of attention of the learners in using the locally-made learning resources yields an average mastery level in their academic performance. The average weighted value, 2.29, with a standard deviation of .98, indicated that the mastery level of the learners is at average mastery. The locally-made learning resources helped the students to learn at an average mastery level. Locally-made learning resources are often designed to address the specific needs and challenges of the local context. By incorporating examples, scenarios, and content that are familiar to learners, these resources can enhance their understanding and application of concepts. This contextual relevance can contribute to improved academic performance

as learners can better relate the content to their own experiences and environments. This corroborated the findings of Twizeyimana et al. (2020) that the use of locally made materials made it easy for students to learn without stress and that they were highly motivated and interested.

Table 5 presents the relationship between the level of effectiveness of locally made learning resources and learners' academic performance. The table shows the variables, computed rho ρ , P-value, and interpretation. The computed rho ρ value, 0.182, produced a P-value that is less than 0.05 level of significance. This means that there was a significant relationship between the level of effectiveness of locally made learning resources and learners' academic performance. It implies that the level of effectiveness of locally made learning resources positively and significantly affects the learners' academic performance. Locally-made learning resources that are designed with the local context in mind can spark learners' interest and motivation. When learners see their own culture, traditions, and experiences reflected in the resources, it can create a sense of ownership and pride in their learning. This increased motivation and engagement can positively impact academic performance by fostering a desire to learn and achieve. Locally-made learning resources can facilitate stronger teacher-student interaction. When teachers use locally-made resources effectively, they can connect with learners on a personal level, fostering a supportive and engaging learning environment. This positive teacher-student interaction can lead to improved academic performance as learners feel valued, supported, and motivated to excel. The result corroborated the findings of Okongo et al. (2015). It revealed that the availability of teaching and learning resources enhances the effectiveness of schools as they are the basic resources that bring about good academic performance in the students. Additionally, Adeogun (2001) discovered a very strong positive significant relationship between instructional resources and academic performance. According to Adeogun, schools endowed with more materials performed better than schools that are less endowed.

Conclusions

The learners believed that the locally made learning resources were relevant and effective, for which they agree that it caught their interest and attention to learn with the locally-made learning resources. Moreover, the locally made learning resources highly and significantly influence their attentiveness, and it also positively affects their academic performance. The locally made learning resources helped the students to learn at an average mastery level and the level of effectiveness of locally made learning resources positively and significantly affects the learners' academic performance.

Recommendations

Through the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. The master teachers should assess the locally-made learning resources along content, delivery, and alignment with the curriculum and identify any areas for improvement or gaps that may be hindering the learners' academic performance.
2. The Dipolog City Schools' top management, through the Learning Resources Management Section, should make programs and policies that will encourage the teachers to enhance the development of locally-made learning resources for the junior high school learners to make it very effective.
3. The Secondary School Administrators, both public and private, should create school-based programs that will support the teachers in enhancing the development of locally-made learning resources.
4. The teachers should develop more and improve the existing locally-made learning resources.
5. The secondary learners should encourage themselves and prioritize the use of locally-made learning resources to assist them in improving their academic performance.
6. While the effectiveness of locally-made learning resources on learners' attentiveness and academic performance has been explored to some extent, there are still areas that warrant further investigation. Future study should focus on investigating the role of teacher training and support in maximizing the effectiveness of locally-made learning resources and the effectiveness of locally-made learning resources in diverse cultural contexts.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The authors have declared that they do not have any conflicts of interest related to the research, authorship, or publication of this article. The authors conducted the study in accordance with the research ethics protocol. The participants were provided with informed consent before receiving the research questionnaire. The data were handled with the highest level of confidentiality.

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